

Sensory evaluation of tactile devices

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Abstract. This study aims to understand how three haptic devices are perceived as buttons by users. In a dim room, 18 participants evaluated the devices. This study enriches the understanding of users' sensory experience by exploring the perception of haptic devices as buttons. The results confirm that the diversity of haptic feedback influences how these devices are interpreted.

Keywords: haptic devices, sensory evaluation, tactile perception, buttons

1 Introduction

We are increasingly using haptic interfaces in various applications to enhance our tactile experiences. Our study investigates how users perceive haptic devices as buttons and proposes to evaluate three tactile devices using sensory evaluation methods [1].

Two prototypes lent by the L2EP laboratory [<https://l2ep.univ-lille.fr/>] were studied and compared to a common commercial device (**iPhone SE**, iOS 17.2.1 featuring a Taptic Engine for vibration and haptic feedback functions).

The first prototype is the **USR60** ultrasonic motor [2] featuring a bronze disk with 16 piezoelectric actuators, connected to a force transducer and microcontroller. Vibrations activate upon exceeding a force threshold; force reset to zero when the user lifts their finger. Parameters were: resonance frequency = 40 kHz, amplitude = 50 V, frequency = 175 Hz, force threshold = 30 g.

The second prototype is the **2MoTac** described in [3] featuring an aluminum plate driven by 9 piezoelectric ceramic actuators. It is mounted on a force sensor, which measures the force at which a participant presses on the plate. Two other plates are added as sensors. Parameters were: resonance frequency = 34 kHz, min force threshold = 15, max force threshold = 25.

2 Material and method

18 participants, aged 20-24 (10 male, 8 female) evaluated the three devices. Assessment occurred in a dim room with devices on a table covered with black textile. Participants touched devices with their index finger until each device was tried randomly.

The questionnaire had three parts. Question 1 (Q1) was an open-ended question about the sensations perceived by user. Question 2 (Q2) consisted of Multiple Choice Questions. Question 3 (Q3) had open-ended questions about potential applications.

3 Results

Fig. 1 lists word families sharing the same root and having related meanings derived from participants’ responses and their occurrences for each device. The word families were obtained from the open-ended responses of Q1 and Q3, then categorized into the “Vibr”, “Press”, “Button”, and “Click” families. For instance, the “Vibr” family counts all words comprising this word root.

Fig. 1. Number of occurrences of each word family for Q1 and Q3

For Q2, the two questions asked were: “The surface of the material is...” and “My finger ...”. Participants were allowed a selection of one or two responses at most. **Fig. 2** illustrates the frequency distribution of each descriptor across various devices.

Fig. 2. Number of descriptors obtained for questions Q2

The final section collected device projections. Using the KJ Method, affinity diagrams organized data thematically [4], [5]. Word clouds (see **Fig. 3**) included 16 words: "Interface", "Relaxation" and "Validation" mentioned 4 times each. iPhone had 11 words: "Warning" and "Phone" mentioned 5 times each. 2MoTac's cloud had 7 words repeated twice, with 34 words mentioned once, making analysis challenging.

Fig. 3. Word cloud from USR60, iPhone and 2MoTac

4 Conclusion

The study contrasts user perceptions of tactile devices: USR60 as a button, iPhone with vibrations, and 2MoTac with mixed perceptions. Using sensory evaluation, it offers novel evaluation methods, yielding detailed insights into user experiences and device-specific perceptions. In conclusion, it provides a comprehensive overview of sensory perceptions, laying the groundwork for future research on tactile button features.

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Disclosure of Interests.

The authors have worked with haptic devices from L2EP.

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